

Similarities between ADHD, Hoarding, Trauma, and Temporal Reward Discounting

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ADHD has several subtypes but is mainly categorized by difficulty focusing on certain tasks. Tasks that are immediately engaging and bring rewards quickly are often easy for individuals diagnosed with ADHD to focus on. In periods of uncertainty it would be reasonable for tasks such as school where the reward is often years in the future to be unattractive in comparison to something with a more immediate reward. I believe this is an underlying mechanism in ADHD symptoms and the way we are framing the problem is incorrect. When looking at its most efficient treatment, amphetamine medication, one of its known side effects is to cause a false sense of well being and to cause loss of appetite or satiation even if the stomach is empty. I believe by creating this false sense of well being, that the rewards are temporally discounted less and the desired behavior outcome is reached.

Temporal discounting can be at the center of several other ADHD symptoms and comorbidities. For example, having issues with money and prioritizing current enjoyment over long-term fiscal well being. Poor hygiene is likely a discounted importance of social contracts and non-essential physiological needs. The same is the case for keeping spaces uncluttered, as this is non-essential to survival. People call this phenomenon clutter-blindness but it might just be completely irrational for them to spend energy on cleaning it in their current state from a survival standpoint. I believe the same to be the case with hoarding, where the value of the item in front of them has increased importance and the long-term social contracts of family members and the long-term health of the home are discounted. It is also found that hoarding symptoms improved significantly with adhd medication treatment with methylphenidate (Grassi et. al).

Stress and trauma being significant causes of ADHD are also supporting factors for this argument. The idea that uncertain environments would foster a tendency towards a shorter-term focus on critical needs is reasonable. Focusing on longer-term needs would leave you vulnerable to short term stressors.